

SCAVENGER HUNT

The first letter of each of the 11 answers can be combined to a solution phrase.
Hand in your solution at the registration desk not later than 04:00 pm on
20. November 2025 to participate in a little tombola!

Hint: The clues can be found only in or around the Klemperer-Saal.

 The clues can be found only in or around the Open Science Lab.

 1 **O**pen Access

 2 **P**ID (Persistent Identifier)

 3 **E**LN (Electronic Lab Notebook)

 4 **N**FDI (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur)

 5 **S**MP (Software Management Plans)

 6 **C**ARE Principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics)

 7 **I**nteroperable

 8 **E**thics Best Practices (Ethics Code / Ethics Guideline)

 9 **N**aming Conventions

 10 **C**reative Commons

 11 **E**OSC (European Open Science Cloud)

.....
(Given name / Surname)

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